

QUALIA SPACE

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Abstract. We define *qualia space* Q to be the space of all possible conscious experience. For simplicity we restrict ourselves to perceptual experience only, though other kinds of experience could also be considered. Qualia space is a highly idealized concept that unifies the perceptual experience of all possible brains. We argue that Q is a closed pointed cone in an infinite-dimensional separable real topological vector space. This quite technical structure can be explained for the most part in a simple, intuitive way. The structure of qualia space allows us to consider and even answer in a precise way such questions as: Is there a continuous path from the sensation of blue to the sensation of pain? Once we fix a desired accuracy of approximation, do there exist finitely many perceptual experiences such that *any* possible perceptual experience is approximately equal to one of them? What should be meant by “fundamentally different” perceptual experiences? There is the possibility of additional structure, such as a Hilbert space structure on the vector space in which Q is embedded.

1. Introduction. There has been much recent investigation of the problem of the location of consciousness.¹ There is a simple tautological solution to this problem which nevertheless raises some interesting additional questions. To a mathematician, the *space* associated with a system is simply the set of all possible states of the system. For instance, our three-dimensional physical universe is just the set of all possible locations of matter and energy. If we also include as part of the system the time when matter and energy occupy a certain position, then the associated space is enlarged to the four-dimensional space-time continuum. The space of a system can be considerably more abstract. For instance, the state of two coupled pendulums constrained to move in a plane is described at a given time by the two space coordinates of each pendulum, and the two momentum coordinates of each pendulum, for a total of eight coordinates. These eight coordinates represent a point in an eight-dimensional space, and the evolution of the system

¹See, for example, (McGinn, 1995) for an overview.

over time is described by a curve in this space. It doesn't make sense to ask "where" this space is actually located; it is just a mathematical abstraction to facilitate our understanding of the system.

From the perspective of the previous paragraph, consciousness is located simply in the space of all possible conscious experience. The question of where this space itself is actually located is irrelevant, if not meaningless.² We will call the space of all possible conscious experience *qualia space*, denoted by Q . Of course because of its abstraction qualia space begs the question raised by McGinn concerning the location of consciousness. It is important to keep in mind that Q is the space of conscious experience of all possible brains, and not of any single brain. Thus we are considering not just all human and animal brains, but all brains that in principle might exist, however alien they might seem to us. Much work has been devoted to the structure of the perceptual experience of a single brain, but this work should not be confused with our object here.

What have we gained by introducing the idea of qualia space? It offers no immediate insight into the many questions surrounding the mystery of consciousness. However, it does suggest that we should try to analyze the structure of this space. Such an analysis must necessarily be highly speculative, since most of the usual tools of science are not available for experimenting on Q . Indeed, large portions of qualia space are literally unknowable to a human mind. In this paper I will attempt a preliminary analysis of the structure of Q . To keep matters relatively simple, I will consider only perceptual consciousness (qualia), and not such aspects of consciousness as emotions, ideas, understanding, etc. Also I will consider only the qualia space of static phenomena and not the conscious awareness of the flow of time, although the discussion could be extended without great difficulty to take time into account. A first basic question we must ask is the following: does Q have any structure at all?³ The statement by (Clarke, 1995, p. 233) that "various thoughts are buzzing around with some kind of togetherness, but without any sort of betweenness, nearness, or any other spatial relation to each other" seems too extreme. It is obvious that Q has *some* structure.

²However, the question of how this space interacts with our own physical universe is still of paramount importance.

³In mathematical terms, is Q a discrete space? A discrete space is just a set of isolated points with no additional structure.

For instance, the sensation of the color blue is “closer” to the sensation of a slightly lighter blue than it is to the sensation of a pain in one’s toe. This intuition suggests that Q will have the structure of a *topological space*. A topological space may be thought of as a space in which there is a concept of “nearby” points.⁴ Thus the sensation of blue is “nearby” that of light blue, and a pain in one’s toe is “nearby” a slightly more intense pain in the same toe or a pain in a slightly different area of the toe.

One way to quantify the idea of nearby points is to define a distance between points. A space with a distance function (satisfying certain commonsense axioms) is called a *metric space*. Every metric space is a topological space, but not conversely. For some brief thoughts on whether Q might have the structure of a metric space, see Section 6. For further information on topological spaces and metric spaces, consult a textbook on topology such as (Munkres, 1975).

The idea that Q is a topological space makes good physical sense. Suppose that a brain B is experiencing certain qualia q . If we change B slightly, such as by slightly increasing the rate of firing of a small group of neurons (or whatever is their equivalent), then we obtain a “nearby” brain B' . It is certainly reasonable to expect that the qualia q' experienced by B' will be “nearby” q . In other words, the fact that our physical universe U is itself a topological space strongly suggests that Q will also be a topological space.⁵ This idea can be used to give a completely rigorous definition of the topological structure of qualia space. Since the details are rather technical, we have relegated them to Appendix 1.

We will be discussing the connection between qualia space and brains at several other points. We regard brains as objects or devices that allow access to qualia space. A brain is therefore a kind of window on or an interface with

⁴The precise definition of a topological space X is extremely abstract. Certain subsets of X are singled out as *open sets*, and certain set-theoretic operations are required to preserve openness. We can then think of two points of X as being “near” if they belong to a “small” open set. In this paper we will use terms like “nearby” in an intuitive way, though everything we say can be made rigorous.

⁵The possibility that the topology of our (human) experience is reflected in the topology of our brains has been suggested by a number of authors, such as (Zeeman, 1962) in the case of visual experience.

qualia space. For each brain B , there is a subset Q_B of qualia space to which it has access.⁶ At the present stage of our knowledge about consciousness, this description of brains should be regarded as no more than a metaphor.

There is an elaborate taxonomy of topological spaces. The mathematician's zoo contains T_0 spaces, Hausdorff spaces, compact spaces, metric spaces, barrelled spaces, Hilbert spaces, manifolds, *ad infinitum*. Here we will consider several fundamental types of topological spaces that seem most relevant to consciousness and ask whether it is reasonable to suppose that Q is one of these types.

2. Connectedness. Perhaps the first question that comes to mind about the structure of Q is whether it is *connected*. For our purposes, this means that there is a continuous curve connecting any two points in Q .⁷ In other words, given two distinct qualia $q(0)$ and $q(1)$, such as the color blue and a pain in the toe, is there a set of qualia $q(t)$, where t is a real number between 0 and 1, that varies *continuously* between $q(0)$ and $q(1)$? (See Figure 1.) One might argue that an intermediate “mixed” state such as $q(1/2)$ cannot exist; there is no sensation halfway between blue and pain that can be experienced by any brain, not just the human brain; blueness and pain are fundamentally different qualia which cannot be averaged. Such an argument, however, is assuming too much about the nature of the path between blueness and pain. Qualia space has a distinguished *base point* or *origin* 0, namely, the absence of any conscious experience. Given any point in Q , such as the sensation of blue, we can imagine slowly decreasing the “intensity” of this point until it finally fades to 0.⁸ Physically this should correspond to a group of neurons firing more slowly, or with less intensity, or in smaller numbers, or less in phase, until finally they reach a state where they give rise to no experience.⁹

⁶As a standard example, the human brain is unable to experience the (presumed) qualia associated with echolocation.

⁷We have really defined the concept of *arcwise connected*. In the most general setting of topological spaces a connected space need not be arcwise connected, but this distinction will not be important for us.

⁸In the human brain, the blueness would turn to grayness before disappearing completely, but this is a special property of our brains (the lack of sensitivity of cones in our retinas to dim light) and not of qualia space in general.

⁹One should not think of this change in the firing of neurons as taking place over time. We are simply describing a continuum of different possible neuronal activities and the corresponding conscious experiences. The different configurations of neurons need not be

Figure 1: A continuous curve $q(t)$ from $q(0)$ to $q(1)$

Similarly we can slowly increase the intensity of any experience, beginning at 0. For instance, colors can become brighter, music louder, pain more intense, etc. Therefore there is a continuous path between any two qualia $q(0)$ and $q(1)$ — let $q(0)$ slowly decrease in intensity to 0, and then increase the intensity in the “ $q(1)$ -direction” until reaching $q(1)$. It follows that Q is indeed connected.

Although the above argument shows the connectedness of Q , we can still ask for a “better” path from $q(0)$ to $q(1)$. For instance, we can ask if there is a path between them that maintains the “intensity” of the experience of $q(0)$ and $q(1)$. Here again there is a simple argument for the affirmative. Begin at $q(0)$ and slowly decrease it to 0, while simultaneously increasing the intensity in the $q(1)$ direction. If the state $q(0)$ is achieved by a certain pattern P_0 of neuron firings, and similarly $q(1)$ by P_1 , then we can imagine beginning only with P_0 , and slowly decreasing their intensity while slowly increasing the intensity of the neurons which achieve P_1 . We can represent symbolically the “mixed state” $q(t)$ for $0 < t < 1$ by the linear combination

realizable by a single brain.

$(1 - t)q(0) + tq(1)$. In the next section we will discuss whether such linear combinations make mathematical sense.

There is still something unsatisfactory about the path $(1 - t)q(0) + tq(1)$ from $q(0)$ to $q(1)$.¹⁰ A point on this path, say $\frac{1}{2}q(0) + \frac{1}{2}q(1)$, represents a simultaneous awareness of $q(0)$ and $q(1)$ at half their intensity, and not a truly new conscious experience. The discussion of paths for which every point is “fundamentally different” will be taken up at the end of the next section.

3. Linearity. A fundamental structure in mathematical models is that of a vector space. In such a space we can add any two points and multiply any point by a real number¹¹, subject to some commonsense axioms. Our own three-dimensional spatial universe is “approximately” a vector space. For reasonably small distances and low densities it looks like a Euclidean space, which is a vector space with certain additional structure (such as a notion of angles). We can then ask if it makes sense to regard qualia space as a vector space. In other words, can we define in a reasonable way what it means to add two conscious experiences and to multiply one by a real number?

Let us consider addition first. If p and q are two points in Q , then we define $p + q$ to be the phenomenal state obtained by experiencing p and q simultaneously. For instance, if p is the experience of blue and q is a pain in a toe, then $p + q$ is the state where we are experiencing simultaneously the color blue and a pain in the toe. We imagine that a certain pattern of neuron firing yields the sensation of blue, while another “unrelated” pattern yields a pain in the toe, with no real connection between them except the binding that causes both sensations to be apprehended by a single mind. The concept of addition of qualia is easy to understand for experiences that seem totally unrelated to each other, but what should be the sum of red and yellow, for instance? One possibility is the simultaneous experiencing of red and yellow “in the same place.” In this case we should see a composite color, presumably orange, since orange seems to us to be a genuine mixture

¹⁰For instance, when (Humphrey, 1992, p. 120) asserts that “by no stretch of the imagination can I get from red to sour, or tickle to A flat,” he undoubtedly has something different in mind than the path $(1 - t)q(0) + tq(1)$.

¹¹We are defining a *real* vector space, i.e., a vector space whose scalars are real numbers. Other fields of scalars are possible but will not be relevant here.

of red and yellow. Another possibility is the simultaneous apprehension of red and yellow at different places of our visual field. We can also imagine a brain connected to red and yellow color receptors, such that the information from the yellow receptors is experienced in a different visual field than that of the red receptors¹². So should the sum of red and yellow be orange, or instead red and yellow in different places of a visual field, or should it be an independent experience of both red and yellow? The problem is that a phenomenal description such as “red” does not give enough information to precisely define the experience. We must be more discriminating and describe the phenomenon as “red in a particular place in a particular visual field” (or, if we want, “red occupying all the space in a particular visual field”). If we call this visual field F , say, then if we add “red in all of F ” to “yellow in all of F ,” we get “orange in all of F .” Similarly, the sum of “red in half of F ” and “yellow in the other half” is the simultaneous experience of red in one half and yellow in the other. On the other hand, if F and G are different visual fields, then the sum of “red in all of F ” and “yellow in all of G ” is simply “red in all of F and yellow in all of G .” Thus the sensation p of red in all of a visual field actually corresponds to infinitely many points p_1, p_2, \dots in qualia space, because in principle a brain could have an arbitrarily large number of completely independent visual processing systems, which come together only in the final binding¹³. The different visual fields are to be regarded as mathematical devices used to distinguish whether different visual phenomena are experienced “compositely” or “independently.” Of course similar reasoning applies to perceptual modes other than vision.

The definition we have given of the sum $p+q$ makes sense when p and q are in some sense “independent,” but what if they are mixed states that overlap? Or, in the extreme case, what if $p = q$? The definition of $p + p$ is subsumed

¹²An additional aspect that we will not consider here is the degree of binding of the red and yellow experiences.

¹³One might argue that such a brain would be so large that the special theory of relativity (which includes the assertion that that no information can be transmitted faster than the speed of light) would preclude it from binding all the visual systems into a single experience. Perhaps it will be necessary to postulate that the linear structure on qualia space only holds in “nonextreme” circumstances. The situation is similar to Hooke’s law of elasticity, which stipulates that there is a linear relationship between the force (stress) exerted on a spring and its length (strain) provided we don’t stretch the spring so far (beyond its elastic limit) that it becomes permanently deformed. Although the linear relationship between stress and strain only holds in a restricted range, it nevertheless is a useful concept.

by our discussion below of multiplication by a real number, since $p + p = 2p$. It corresponds to the state p with its intensity doubled. For instance, blue + blue is a blue that is twice as bright. More general mixed states are added componentwise. For instance, $(2p + q) + (3p + 2r) = 5p + q + 2r$.

There might still be some confusion over the addition of certain states. For instance, suppose that p is the visual experience of a human enjoying a beautiful mountain sunset. Let q be the visual experience of a frog who is about to catch a fly on his or her tongue. What should be the sum $p + q$? As discussed above, we must specify in describing p and q whether the visual experience of a human watching a sunset and a frog catching a fly occurs in the same visual field or not. Perhaps it is impossible for these two experiences to occupy the same visual field; the visual field of a frog is “inherently different” from the field of a human, and it is contradictory to identify them in some imagined mind. If this is the case, then $p + q$ must refer to two independent visual fields, one with the human’s experience and one with the frog’s (apprehended simultaneously by a single mind). But if we can superimpose a human’s and a frog’s vision, then we must specify whether p and q refer to the same visual field. If they do, then $p + q$ is this strange superimposed visual state.

Let us turn to the general question of *scalar multiplication*, that is, multiplication of a state p by a real number α . If $\alpha \geq 0$ then we can think of αp as a scaling of the intensity of p by a factor of α . The precise definition of how much change in intensity of p is $1.35p$, say, would presumably have a neural correlate, such as a certain percentage change in the rate, intensity, phase, or number of neurons firing.¹⁴ For certain qualia like vision it should be easier to quantify exactly what is meant by αp than for other states like pain, but we will just assume that there is some reasonable way to quantify the change in intensity of a state.

It may seem strange that we are allowing multiplication of a state p by an *arbitrarily large* real number α . Can there really exist brains that experience, for instance, light of arbitrarily high brightness?¹⁵ (This question is

¹⁴There is an extensive literature on the intensity of human perceptual experience and its neural and physical correlates, as part of the subject of *psychophysics*. See (Gescheider, 1985) or (Stevens, 1975) for further information.

¹⁵Actually, the light itself is irrelevant. The real question is whether the *experience*

similar to the one raised in footnote 13.) At the idealized level that we are considering qualia space, there is no obvious reason to exclude this possibility. Since there can theoretically exist light of arbitrary brightness¹⁶, why shouldn't there exist a corresponding conscious awareness of such light? If there is anything to Chalmers's theory of "naturalistic dualism" (Chalmers, 1996, Ch. 4) or other similar theories, then it is reasonable to suppose that any physical phenomenon has an experiential counterpart. If physical systems can have arbitrarily large energies, why shouldn't the corresponding experiential counterpart have arbitrarily large "intensities"?

Though multiplication of a state by a *nonnegative* real number has a reasonable intuitive definition, there does not seem to be anything comparable for multiplication by a *negative* real number. If the intensity of a state is correlated with neuronal activity, then it is impossible to be less active than "off," which is the 0 state¹⁷. A subset of a (real) vector space closed under addition and closed under multiplication by nonnegative real numbers is called a *cone*. Thus we are claiming that Q is a cone in a vector space V . Moreover, Q is a *pointed* cone, meaning that Q does not contain both a nonzero state p and its negative $-p$. The vector space V consists of *all* linear combinations (i.e., allowing positive and negative coefficients) of the elements of Q . We call V the space of *virtual qualia*; a point in V may be regarded as a "virtual conscious experience." Our argument that Q is a cone elucidates its idealized nature; certainly the perceptual space of no single (finite) brain can be expected to be a cone.¹⁸

that we associate with light can have an arbitrarily high intensity. In general we are not concerned with the *cause* of an experience, but only with the experience *per se*. Note also that we are not requiring a single brain to experience light of arbitrary brightness, but rather for any specified brightness there exists *some* brain that can experience it.

¹⁶Perhaps for physical reasons arbitrarily bright light cannot occur (e.g., because of the finite size of the universe, or because light might start converting to matter after reaching a certain degree of brightness). Such physical considerations could have an experiential analogue. Our investigation is at such a rudimentary stage that we will ignore such subtleties here.

¹⁷In the human brain, for instance, the opponent process theory of color vision (Hardin, 1988, Ch. I) suggests that we can think of red as negative green and of blue as negative yellow. However, this opponency is a special property of our brains and does not correspond to any intuitive notion of negation. There is no reason to believe that red and green are opposed in this way in all possible brains.

¹⁸Note also that if we allow nonperceptual conscious experience into qualia space, then the cone structure might break down. If p is the belief that there are infinitely many prime

The topological and linear (i.e., cone) structure on Q are compatible in the sense that if p is near q and p' is near q' , then (1) $p+p'$ is near $q+q'$, and (2) αp is near $\alpha p'$ for any $\alpha \geq 0$. These assertions make good intuitive sense, as may be seen by considering some examples. For instance, blue is near light blue, and a pain in a toe is near a pain in a slightly different location. Hence the simultaneous experience of blue and a pain in a toe is near the simultaneous experience of light blue and a nearby pain. It follows that Q is more than a topological space and a cone in a vector space independently, but is in fact a cone in a *topological vector space*.

There is one further property of the cone Q that deserves mention, namely, it is *closed* in the vector space V of virtual qualia. This means, essentially, that if p is a point in V but p is not a point of Q , then points “nearby” p also do not belong to Q . We will not belabor this point, but it makes good sense. For instance, if p is the sensation of blue (of a certain positive brightness), then $-p$ does not belong to Q , and hence also points close to $-p$ such as $-.99p$ do not belong to Q .

The concept of linearity allows us to make more precise the idea of “fundamentally different” phenomenal experiences, as discussed at the end of Section 2. Let us define two points p and q in qualia space to be *unrelated* if there do not exist points p' , q' and r in Q , with $r \neq 0$, such that $p = p' + r$ and $q = q' + r$. Informally, no part of p is also a part of q . For instance, blue and pain should be unrelated, as should blue experiences in disjoint parts of a visual field. However, blue experiences that overlap in a visual field will not be unrelated. The concept of unrelated points seems to capture well the idea of fundamentally different phenomenal experiences. We can then say that a path P from p to q is “nice” if all points on P are unrelated. We don’t see how to answer the question of whether there is such a path from blue to pain, for instance, by logical reasoning alone. The fact that we are unable to imagine such a path of course proves nothing, since our brains by necessity are unable to imagine phenomenal experiences that they are incapable of perceiving. Some experimentation with qualia space, at present a completely impossible undertaking, will be necessary to resolve this question.

4. Dimension. A fundamental invariant of any vector space is its *dimension*, then what could $2p$ be?

mension d , the maximum number of linearly independent elements in the space. Equivalently, d is the minimum number of parameters (real numbers) necessary to specify (in a reasonable way) a point p in the space. Similarly we can define the dimension of a cone in a vector space. It is obvious that the dimension of Q is infinite. For instance, just to describe a visual field requires specifying the visual qualia (hue, brightness, etc.) at each of the infinitely many points of the field.¹⁹ Thus not only is the dimension of Q infinite, but it is *uncountably infinite*, that is, the parameters necessary to describe a point cannot be enumerated in a list $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots$ ²⁰

The uncountable nature of qualia space is even more fundamental than the above discussion suggests. For instance, the human retina has three different kinds of color receptors (or four, if we wish to take into account also the achromatic rods), corresponding to the fact that the dimension of human “color space” is three, in the sense that the sensation of every color can be obtained from combinations of only three colors.²¹ We can imagine, however, a brain with any (finite) number of kinds of color receptors, each kind sensitive to a different wavelength of light (or of other wavelengths on the electromagnetic spectrum) and each resulting in a “fundamentally different” quale²². In the limit there will be a different kind of receptor for *every* wavelength of light. Thus just the “color subspace” of qualia space has uncountably infi-

¹⁹For a particular brain there is a limit on the resolution of the visual field, so we don’t really need infinitely much data to describe the field. Perhaps the laws of quantum mechanics, the finite size of atoms, or some other obstacle limits the resolution of the visual field of *any* brain. Our idealized view of qualia space ignores such considerations, as also suggested in footnote 16.

²⁰We are using the fact, due to Cantor *via* his famous diagonalization argument, that the real numbers are uncountably infinite. The points in even a one-dimensional visual field are in one-to-one correspondence with the real numbers, so it takes uncountably many parameters to specify qualia for each point.

²¹We have greatly oversimplified the true description of human color vision (Hardin, 1988). True color space for humans is not a vector space, and its dimension (whose value is still subject to controversy) should be thought of (roughly) as the minimum number of parameters necessary to specify a point in the space. The essential point here that the dimension of human color space is small remains valid.

²²We are correlating color qualia with wavelength for illustrative purposes only. We are not concerned here with *how* a particular phenomenal state arises in a brain. We are also ignoring, as we have done previously, the problem that a brain with sufficiently many color receptors would not fit in our visible universe. At the level of abstraction we are dealing with, we can imagine a universe as large as we want.

nite dimension. A brain that approximates this behavior of a fundamentally different quale for each wavelength would have an unimaginably rich visual experience. There would be (in the limit) an entire continuum of primary colors, and any mixture of these colors would be distinguishable from any other mixture!

5. Separability. We have argued in the previous section that qualia space has uncountably infinite dimension. This fact, however, does not really give an accurate picture of the “size” of Q . It is necessary to take the topological structure of Q into account. A topological space X is called *separable* if it contains a countable dense set.²³ This means that there exists a sequence of points p_1, p_2, \dots in X such that given any point p in X , we can find a point p_i as close as we want to p . For instance, the space of real numbers, though uncountable, is separable. The rational numbers form a countable dense set, since it is known since Cantor how to enumerate the rational numbers in a sequence p_1, p_2, \dots , and every real number is arbitrarily close to (can be approximated as accurately as desired by) a rational number. If a topological vector space X is separable, then X contains a *countable* linearly independent subset B such that every element of X is “arbitrarily close” to a linear combination of elements of B .

To say that qualia space is separable would mean that we can find a sequence $p_1, p_2 \dots$ of perceptual states such that every possible perceptual state p is as close as we want to one of the p_i 's. (The choice of p_i depends on how close we want it to be to p .) One's first reaction might be that the possible perceptual states are so diverse and unknowable²⁴ that there may very well be no countable list that approximates each one arbitrarily closely. In other words, the number of possible perceptual states is “essentially uncountable.” And even if this is not the case, how could we possibly know it? But there is a simple argument that strongly suggests that Q is separable. The key point is that the space of all possible *brains* is separable. A brain B is a finite object made out of finitely many electrons, protons, and neutrons (or even further particles if such detail is really necessary). Choose a positive integer n , and divide the entire visible universe into little cubes whose side

²³An alternative, somewhat more technical definition of “separable” is sometimes used. See for example (Lang, 1983, p. 23).

²⁴For instance, there may even be qualia for abstract concepts like numbers, as suggested by reports of *idiot savants* such as in (Sacks, 1987, Chapter 23).

length is $1/n$ meters. For each particle (electron, proton, or neutron) in the brain B , move it to the center of the cube in which its center of mass lies. (We may assume n is so large that no two particles are moved to the same point.) In a similar manner we can specify the momentum of each particle to a predetermined degree of accuracy²⁵. When n is extremely large (say when $1/n$ meters is less than 10^{-30} times the diameter of a proton), the resulting configuration B' should be an extremely close approximation of B . We expect that B' will also have conscious awareness, and that its conscious state will be approximately the same as B 's. And as n becomes even larger, the approximation becomes even more accurate. Standard mathematical arguments, familiar since Cantor, show that the total number of these approximations to *all* possible (finite) brains is countable. The set of all perceptual states of these brain approximations will be a countable dense subset of qualia space. Hence qualia space is separable.

The above reasoning has an additional consequence. If we put a bound on the total number of particles that can occur in a brain B (say the total number of particles in the visible universe, to be extravagantly generous) and fix an extremely large value of the integer n that measures the closeness of the approximation B' , then there are only *finitely* many possible brain approximations, but we expect them for all practical purposes to achieve *every* possible perceptual state.

6. Orthogonality. There are many additional structures that can be put on a topological space. One of the nicest and most useful is the structure of a Hilbert space, for which there is a notion of an “inner product” or “scalar product” between two points that allows us to define the angle between two intersecting lines, the distance between two points, etc. It seems difficult, however, to come up with a sensible intuitive definition of the inner product $\langle p, q \rangle$ of two conscious states p and q . However, there is a special case of the inner product that seems promising. Namely, two points p, q in a Hilbert space are said to be *orthogonal* if $\langle p, q \rangle = 0$. This means geometrically that the lines joining the points to the origin are perpendicular (form an angle of 90°). In some sense, orthogonal points are as “independent as possible.”

²⁵For simplicity we are adopting here a classical (Newtonian) viewpoint. To incorporate quantum mechanics, one should approximate each particle’s wave function. Such considerations are not really relevant to our argument.

To what might orthogonal points in qualia space correspond? We suggest that two points (conscious states) are orthogonal if they are “of different phenomenal type.” For instance, the sensation of blue would be orthogonal to the sensation of middle C, because vision and sound are “different types” of conscious states. On the other hand, blue and red would not be orthogonal, because they are both experiences of the same type, namely, vision. The notion of being of different type is thus much stronger than the notion of being fundamentally different or unrelated as defined in Section 3. The above definition of orthogonality is admittedly vague and imprecise. I don’t know a rigorous mathematical way to capture this intuitive notion of orthogonality of conscious states. Appendix 2 at the end of this paper points out a further difficulty in coming up with a good definition of orthogonality.

In Section 3 we discussed “nice” paths of unrelated phenomenal experiences between two points p and q . Since being of a different type, as defined in the previous paragraph, is even stronger than being unrelated, we can ask about the existence of a path between p and q all of whose points are of different phenomenal type. Intuitively such a path seems unlikely, and indeed if we interpret points of different type as orthogonal then this intuitive notion can be made mathematically precise. If p is any nonzero point in qualia space, then points nearby p cannot be orthogonal to p , since $\langle p, p \rangle > 0$ and the scalar product in a Hilbert space is continuous. Hence no two distinct points in Q can be connected by a path of orthogonal points.

There might be neural correlates to our notion of orthogonality. Orthogonal events would only be brought together in the brain at the very last stages of processing. However, this necessary condition for orthogonality does not seem sufficient. We discussed earlier a putative brain that processes visual input from two receptors completely independently. We probably do not want to think of these two vision experiences as orthogonal. Further work needs to be done to come up with a precise definition of orthogonality of conscious states, and whether it can be incorporated into a more general Hilbert space structure.

7. Conclusion. We have argued that Q has the structure of a closed pointed cone in an infinite-dimensional separable real topological vector space. The structural conditions on Q lead to certain conclusions, such as the existence of unrelated or fundamentally different experiences. There is a pos-

sibility that Q may possess further structure, such as being contained in a Hilbert space.

Is there any hope that the structure of Q can be examined by the experimental tools and scientific methods that we use to study the physical universe? Perhaps some day it will be possible to connect the human brain with machines so as to expand the phenomenal experience available to the human mind (as has been suggested by many scientists and science fiction writers). When this distant day arrives we can begin a purely scientific study of qualia space.

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APPENDIX 1

In this appendix we give a precise definition of qualia space as a quotient space. The first step is to define a topology on the space \mathcal{B} of all possible brains. We regard a brain simply as a finite collection of particles with specified positions and momenta. If we fix the number of particles of each kind (for instance, 10^{25} protons, 17×10^{25} neutrons, etc.), then we can describe the position and momentum of these particles as a single point in a configuration space. It is easy to define a topological structure on this configuration space. Then for each specification S of the number of particles of each type, we have a different configuration space X_S . The disjoint union of these spaces X_S will be the topological space \mathcal{B} of brains²⁶. We now define two brains (at a given instant of time) to be *equivalent* if their perceptual experiences are identical. This definition of equivalence is an equivalence relation, and we define qualia space Q to be the quotient space of brain space \mathcal{B} with respect to this equivalence relation. In other words, the elements of Q are the equivalence classes of brains, and the topology on Q is the finest topology that makes the projection map $B \rightarrow Q$ (which takes each brain B to its equivalence class) continuous.

APPENDIX 2

²⁶One could argue for a different topological structure on \mathcal{B} , but this is irrelevant for our purposes.

In this appendix we point out a technical difficulty in imposing a Hilbert space structure on the vector space V of virtual qualia. Suppose that V can be given a Hilbert space structure so that the orthogonality of elements of Q corresponds to different phenomenal type. This definition of orthogonality is not sufficient to determine the orthogonality of *any* two points of V (not just of points of Q). For instance, if p is the sensation of blue and q the sensation of red, then p and q are linearly independent but not orthogonal. There is then a unique real number α such that $p + \alpha q$ and q are orthogonal (simply solve the equation $\langle p, q \rangle + \alpha \langle q, q \rangle = 0$ for α). Moreover, $p + \alpha q \neq 0$ since p and q are linearly independent. Thus we must have $\alpha < 0$; otherwise, $p + \alpha q$ and q would be orthogonal points *contained in* Q , yet $p + \alpha q$ and q are not of different phenomenal type. (This argument also shows that $\langle p, q \rangle > 0$, since $\langle q, q \rangle > 0$ for any nonzero point q in a Hilbert space.) Thus q is orthogonal to some point $p + \alpha q$ in V but not in Q , and there is no reasonable intuitive way to decide what is the value of α .

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